

Spatial pattern formation of a predator-prey system with predator pursuit and prey evasion

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Abstract

Spatial synchrony, which can be result of high migration, can increase the risk of regional extinction, and as a result reduce metapopulation persistence. Coupled patch models, based on a within-patch discrete growth model, are used to investigate the impact of predator pursuit (PP) and prey evasion (PE) on spatial synchrony and pattern formation in a metapopulation framework. Results show that PP and PE together can reduce spatial synchrony and thus the improvement of metapopulation persistence. PP and PE on their own do not significantly contribute towards asynchrony, however, they do contribute towards higher average population sizes, which in turn results in the improvement of metapopulation persistence. Spatially explicit predator-prey systems with local migration without PP and PE can produce self-organized spatial patterns such as spiral waves and circular waves. The effect of PP and PE on spatial pattern formation can decrease spatial synchrony and change the spiral and circular waves to spatial chaos which result in asynchrony of neighbouring patches and improve metapopulation persistence.

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List of Reserved Symbols

Symbol	Meaning
N_t	Size of prey population at time t .
P_t	Size of predator population at time t .
$N_{i,t}$	Size of prey population in patch i at time t .
$P_{i,t}$	Size of predator population in patch i at time t .
$N_{i,t}^M$	Size of post-migration prey population in patch i at time t .
$P_{i,t}^M$	Size of post-migration predator population in patch i at time t .
a	Rate of predator attack.
b	Rate of growth in prey population.
c	Rate of growth in predator population.
K	Maximum Size of prey population (Carrying Capacity).
r	Rate of growth in arbitrary population.
μ	Rate of per capita migration of prey.
α	Rate of per capita migration of predator.
ν	Effect intensity of prey evasion.
β	Effect intensity of predator pursuit.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Biological Background

Ecological communities often consist of a vast number of species where their existence is almost synonymous to unending change. These changes can, for example, be a result of demographic dynamics (births, deaths, spatial movement), interspecific interactions (e.g. competition and predation) and environmental disturbance (e.g. habitat destruction and resource depletion). Understanding the mechanisms behind these changes in population sizes is the central theme in population ecology. Of special interest to this study, predation has received much attention in mathematics due to the dynamic complexity inherent in predator-prey systems. Predation can be defined as a mode of life in which food is primarily obtained by killing and consuming organisms. A predator is an organism that depends on predation for its food. A prey is an organism that is or may be seized by a predator to be eaten. A predator-prey system consists of two or more species-populations (i.e. predator and prey populations) living together and interacting.

Most communities, in the absence of outside disturbance, either remain in a steady-state for long periods of time, or pass through orderly fluctuation patterns. In contrast to this steadiness, examples of sudden population explosions or extinction occur [23]. A key factor causing such sudden population explosions or extinction is interspecific interactions. Interspecific interactions include competition, predator-prey or host-parasite relationships, symbiosis (in which the presence of each species benefits the other), commensalism (in which the first species benefits from the second but the second is unaffected by the first) and amensalism (in which the first species is inhibited by the second but the second is unaffected by the first and can also be described as ‘one-sided competition’). A good example of population explosion is the human population which have increased dramatically during the past 200 years as a result of the industrial and medical revolution (see Figure 1.1). One might see this as the human population out-competing and inhibiting all other species. Predictions have been made that the human population would soon start declining due to limiting factors such as food resources [13]. The Lake Victoria and Nile Perch catastrophe in 1960 is a classical example of sudden population explosion and extinction in the presence of outside disturbance. Here, the introduction of the large predator species (Nile Perch) in the lake, which was thought to provide a high-yielding and valuable source of protein, have essentially wiped out the several hundred smaller cichlid fish in the lake in a couple of years time. Even more serious is the fact that many of the cichlid species helped to control the level of a particular snail which lives in and around the lake. These freshwater snails are an essential link in the cycle of the parasitic disease called schistosomiasis

(also known as bilharzia)[20]. All these examples of explosion and extinction of populations lead to two important questions that have been confronting ecologists:

- 1) What are the processes that permit maintenance of a steady-state; and
- 2) What are the causes and consequences of sudden departures from steadiness.

Figure 1.1: Long-term world population growth, 1750-2050. (Source: United Nations Population Division, 'The World at Six Billion')

In their quest to answer these ecological questions, various studies have been performed to try to understand more of the underlying processes which allows population persistence or extinction. One of the outcomes of these studies was the metapopulation methodology. The term *metapopulation* arrived in the ecological literature in 1969, to describe a population of local(sub) populations. Populations are defined as groups of interacting individuals with a finite lifetime, whereas metapopulations are systems of such local populations with a finite lifetime, connected by migrating individuals. The metapopulation concept is thus closely linked with the processes of population turnover, extinction and the establishment of new populations. The study of metapopulation dynamics is thus essentially the study of the conditions under which these processes are in balance. Due to habitat destruction and fragmentation around the world, many species with a formerly continuous spatial distribution are being turned into possible metapopulations. The dynamics of such fragmented populations need to be understood so that relevant management remedies may be attempted to prevent total extinction. Metapopulation framework have thus become the vogue in conservation biology, and it seems clear that much of the current and future metapopulation research will be motivated by and applied to conservation biology [12].

In a metapopulation context, migrating individuals may follow some density-dependent rules such as predator pursuit and prey evasion. Predator pursuit (PP) indicates that predators migrate not only from subpopulations of higher predator density to those of lower predator density as from natural diffusion, but also from subpopulations of lower prey density to those of higher prey density. Prey evasion (PE), on the other hand, indicates that prey migrate not only from subpopulations of higher prey density to those of lower prey density as from natural diffusion, but also from subpopulations of higher predator density to those of lower predator

density [18]. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect which PP and PE has on metapopulation persistence.

1.2 Problem Description

The idea that migration among subpopulations may allow the persistence of regional metapopulations, despite unstable fluctuations and even extinctions locally, has long been important in ecology. An especially popular application of this idea has been to predator-prey interactions as a way of reconciling their persistence in nature with the fact that spatially simple predator-prey systems, both in the laboratory and in models, tend to be unstable to the point of extinction [29]. Theoretical and laboratory studies have shown that even though subpopulations are unstable, connecting them through migration can have a stabilizing effect on the metapopulation (provided some conditions are met) and therefore result in metapopulation persistence [7].

The fundamental requirement of persistence through migration is asynchrony of subpopulation fluctuations. Synchronized subpopulations can lead to local extinctions with no recolonizations possible from their synchronized neighbours, and therefore lead to metapopulation extinction. Fragmented populations thus possess an intriguing duplicity: even if subpopulations are reliably extinction-prone, asynchrony in local extinctions and recolonizations makes metapopulation persistence possible [18, 5]. Persistence also places requirements on migration rates: too little migration prevents recolonization of extinct patches, whereas too much synchronizes subpopulations, raising the likelihood of global extinction [7, 4]. Another requisite for metapopulation persistence is that there be some local density-dependent factor(s) [29]. Two such density-dependent migration rules, namely Predator Pursuit (PP) and Prey Evasion (PE), have been investigated in the study by Li *et al.* [18] by the use of dispersion terms rather than the traditional diffusion terms used in continuous models to capture spatial movement of species. Diffusion differs from dispersion in the sense that diffusion tends to be a passive process caused by a natural tendency to move from high density subpopulations to lower density subpopulations. Dispersion, on the other hand, is an active process caused by actively pursuing or evading to neighbouring subpopulations with higher or lower prey and predator densities. The migration rules PP and PE have been shown to reduce spatial synchrony and therefore result in the improvement of metapopulation persistence.

The model used by Li *et al.* was based on differential equations, and hence assumes overlapping generations. In this study we will investigate the effect of PP and PE on spatial synchrony (and hence metapopulation persistence) with a model based on difference equations, and hence assuming non-overlapping generations (or strongly seasonal life cycles). This study have therefore in mind primarily insect predator-prey systems. Examples of such systems include the larvae of mayflies and their stone-fly predators, tadpoles and larval dragonflies, and spiders and grasshoppers.

1.3 Possible Applications

An important conservation application in the study of insect predator-prey systems are the use of natural predators for pest control to inhibit any large pest increase by a corresponding increase in the predator population. The aim is to keep both populations at acceptably low levels in the long term. The aim is not to eradicate the pest due to the extremely high cost, only to control its population. Examples include the use of the carabid beetle *Pterostichus cupreus*

as a natural predator to the bird-cherry oat aphid *Rhopalosiphum padi*. The aphid is considered an important pest on cereal spring crops in Sweden [3]. The introduction of the carabid beetle as a bio-control agent in this case has successfully kept the aphid population low.

Another important conservation application of metapopulation studies is the long debated subject on how game reserves should be designed. The most important goal of a game reserve is the conservation of species. Many different factors, which include habitat preference, migration and climate change, need to be taken into account. The main question behind the debate, namely whether it is better to create several small reserves or one large reserve, was labelled as SLOSS - Single Large Or Several Small. Biologists favouring a single large reserve argue that since species richness increases with habitat area, a larger habitat would support more species than any of the smaller habitats [8]. Biologists favouring several small reserves argue that if the smaller reserves have unshared species, then it is possible that two smaller reserves can have more species than a single large reserve [27]. Furthermore, biologists also speculate on whether asynchrony between subpopulations (and thus better metapopulation persistence) might be better maintained by several small reserves connected by migration or by one single large reserve. In the modern world migration between small reserves would typically be in an artificial form through human intervention.

From studying interaction models we know that a system can be driven unstable if certain parameters are changed appropriately, that is, pass through bifurcation values. It should therefore be a matter of considerable scientific study before any system is altered by external manipulation such as biological pest control. It should also be kept in mind that there is a whole web of interacting species, which makes for structurally complex communities. The use of models to study the effect of artificial interference in trophic webs is essential and can be extremely illuminating. Had this been done it is likely that the Lake Victoria and Nile Perch catastrophe in 1960 would have been avoided [20].

Chapter 2

Literature Review

“The one and only substitute for experience which we have not ourselves had is literature.”

— Alexander Solzhenitsyn

In this chapter the necessary background to understand this study have been summarised. Firstly, to understand where the mathematical models incorporated originated, a historical background of growth and interaction models is given. Secondly, to understand the improvement that individual based and metapopulation modelling brought, an overview of the underlying assumption of most traditional models is given, namely, the mean-field assumption. Thirdly, an historic overview of metapopulation modelling, which is the mathematical approach used in this study, is given. In the last paragraph one of the techniques to test metapopulation stability, which will be used in this study, is given.

2.1 Historical background of mathematical models

All populations of organisms fluctuate in size. The only assertion that can be made with certainty for any population is that its size will not remain constant. It is therefore not surprising that the oldest branch of mathematical ecology is the investigation of the increase and decline of populations¹[23].

Ecologists found that a fruitful way to model population growth is to postulate a simple model to account for population change and then to examine the consequences of the assumptions by mathematical argument [23]. A number of models that describe population growth and interaction between species are discussed in this section, including Malthusian growth, Logistic growth, Lotka-Volterra predator-prey interaction and Nicholson-Bailey predator-prey interaction models.

¹Population growth is the change in population over time, and can be quantified as the change in the number of individuals in a population using *per unit time* for measurement

2.1.1 Malthusian growth

The first population growth model was introduced in 1790 by Reverend Thomas Malthus. In this model the rate of change in population density, with respect to time, is proportional to the population density. Written as a differential equation, it takes the form

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = rN \quad (2.1)$$

where N denotes the population density, r the intrinsic growth rate, and t the time. Solving the equation yields

$$N(t) = N_0 e^{rt} \quad (2.2)$$

where N_0 denotes the initial population. The *Malthusian growth model* is thus essentially exponential growth based on a constant rate of compound interest. This model is often referred to as *The Exponential Law* and is widely regarded in the field of population ecology as the first principle of population dynamics.

At best, it can be described as an approximate physical law as it is generally acknowledged that nothing can grow at a constant rate indefinitely. The simplicity of the model makes it useful for very short-term predictions [6, 31].

2.1.2 Logistic growth

Populations do not tend to infinity as in Malthusian growth, there is always some external limiting factor (food limitation, space limitation, etc.) which cause the population to tend to some finite limit. In 1838 Pierre Francois Verhulst introduced the *Logistic growth model* with equations of the form

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = rN\left(1 - \frac{N}{K}\right) \quad (2.3)$$

where K represent the carrying capacity or the maximum number of individuals supported by the environment [32]. The population size converges to the carrying capacity in this model.

2.1.3 Discrete logistic growth

For many species, population growth is markedly discontinuous (in discrete steps). For primitive organisms these can be quite short in which case a continuous (in time) model may be a reasonable approximation. However, depending on the species the step lengths can vary widely. A year is common. With fruit fly emergence from pupae is a day, where for cells it can be a number of hours [19]. Species with discrete population growth are those whose members reproduce only once in their lifetimes and die before their descendents' lives begin; that is, each generation dies before the eggs it has laid hatch (or the seeds it has set germinate) to form the succeeding generation [23]. An example would be a species of insects that lay their eggs in the soil in the autumn and then die while the next generation is born the next spring. Another example includes the Australian marsupial mouse, which has an unusual life-history for a mammal. The mice are seasonal breeders that mature at age one year and die after

mating [17]. A continuous-time differential equation is then inappropriate as a representation of population growth and a difference equation is a more suitable model [19].

A discrete logistic growth model was proposed by Ricker in 1954 [24] with equations given by

$$N_{t+1} = N_t e^{r(1 - \frac{N_t}{K})} \quad (2.4)$$

where N_t represents the number of individuals at time t , r the intrinsic growth rate, and K the carrying capacity or the maximum number of individuals supported by the environment. The population size converges to the carrying capacity as in the continuous logistic growth model.

2.1.4 Lotka-volterra model

One of the earliest of all host-parasitoid (or predator-prey) interaction models is that devised by Lotka (1925) and independently by Volterra [26]. The interaction between two species is accounted for by a system of quadratic differential equations given by

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dN}{dt} = (a - bP)N \\ \frac{dP}{dt} = (-c + dN)P \end{cases} \quad (2.5)$$

with $a, b, c, d > 0$. N and P denote the densities of prey and predators, a denotes the intrinsic growth rate per individual of the prey species in the absence of predators, b the predator attack rate, c is the predator death rate in the absence of prey, and d is the conversion efficiency of prey into adult predators of the next generation. The predator population goes extinct in the absence of prey, since food (prey) are necessary for survival. Predator increase is directly proportional to the number of prey present.

Lotka and Volterra worked out some of the mathematical properties of the system. They showed that, in the case of predation or parasitism, the solution is a family of closed periodic curves, depending on the initial sizes of the two populations (the system has neutral stability). Small oscillations in the neighborhood of a unique fixed point was recognized to be well approximated by ellipses, and the period of the oscillations is almost independent of their amplitude [26]. In a system governed by this model, both prey and predator populations would therefore undergo constant oscillations whose amplitudes would bear no relation to the biology of the two species but only to the initial sizes of their populations which could be quite arbitrary [23].

The underlying assumption in the Lotka-Volterra model is that each species' growth rate depends only on the other species' population size with no self limitation. In the case of prey, Malthusian growth would be experienced in the absence of predators. This assumption makes the Lotka-Volterra model rather unrealistic. More realistic models have been developed and used successfully in later studies which incorporates prey and predator limiting factors (where prey would follow logistic growth in the absence of predators). Examples of such models include the predator-prey model of Ronsenzweig and MacArthur [25] with equations given by

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dN}{dt} = rN(1 - \frac{N}{K}) - \frac{bNP}{b+N} \\ \frac{dP}{dt} = \frac{bNP}{b+N} - dP \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

where N and P denote the densities of prey and predators, r the prey growth rate, K the carrying capacity of the prey population, b the saturation value of the functional response, and d the predator death rate in the absence of prey. The population dynamics for this model is stable for small prey carrying capacity, and oscillate periodically for large carrying capacity (stable limit cycle behaviour).

2.1.5 Nicholson-Bailey model

The Nicholson-Bailey model was developed in the 1930's by Nicholson and Bailey [22] to describe the population dynamics of a coupled host-parasite (or predator-prey) system with discrete generation. The equations are given by

$$\begin{cases} N_{t+1} &= bN_t e^{-aP_t} \\ P_{t+1} &= cN_t(1 - e^{-aP_t}) \end{cases} \quad (2.7)$$

where N_t and P_t represents the population sizes of susceptible prey and searching adult female predators at time t , b denotes the prey reproductive rate, and c denotes the average number of female predators produced per prey. The parameter a was termed the *area of discovery*, which was thought to be a species-specific constant defining the lifetime rate of encounters between prey and a single searching predator. In other words, a denotes the attack rate of the predator. To distribute encounters among prey, Nicholson and Bailey assumed that predators searched at random, and thus would re-encounter space previously searched. A Poisson model was used to distribute encounters (N_e) among prey (N_t). The general form of the Poisson model is:

$$Prob(X = m) = e^{-A} \left(\frac{A^m}{m!} \right) \quad (2.8)$$

where $Prob(X = m)$ is the probability of m occurrences and A is the average occurrence of X .

In the Nicholson-Bailey model, since it is assumed that prey and predators encounter each other randomly, the total number of encounters per unit time (N_e) is proportional to the product of prey and predator densities. That is, $N_e = aNP$. Therefore, the average number of encounters per prey is given by

$$A = \frac{N_e}{N_t} = aP_t \quad (2.9)$$

The probability that a prey escapes predation is equal to the probability that a prey encounters 0 predators, which is the zero term of the Poisson distribution. Thus,

$$Prob(X = 0) = e^{-aP_t} \quad (2.10)$$

and the probability of being attacked (being encountered one or more times)

$$Prob(X > 0) = 1 - e^{-aP_t} \quad (2.11)$$

Inserting these statements of probability into equations of prey and predator population growth gives the Nicholson-Bailey model [2]. In its basic form, it is always unstable (for all parameter

values) and does not even allow persistence of the system (*i.e.*, permanent coexistence of the interacting species) [16]. Figure 2.1 illustrates the population density over time using the Nicholson-Bailey model.

Figure 2.1: Population density cycles over time using the Nicholson-Bailey model with parameter values set as $a = 0.8$, $b = 1.5$, $c = 2$. Both species goes extinct after 37 generations.

2.1.6 Nicholson-Bailey model with saturated prey

The form of the Nicholson-Bailey equations implies that the number of encounters a predator has with a prey increases unboundedly with the prey density which seems rather unrealistic. It is more likely that there is a limit to the predators' appetite. Also, another way of looking at it is that in the absence of predators, the prey population would grow unboundedly following simple Malthusian growth.

The prey equation of the Nicholson-Bailey model need to incorporate some saturation of the prey population or, in terms of predator encounters, a prey-limiting factor. The Nicholson-Bailey model was modified in 1975 by Beddington *et al.* [1] to incorporate a saturation level of the prey population with equations given by

$$\begin{cases} N_{t+1} &= N_t e^{b(1-\frac{N_t}{K})-aP_t} \\ P_{t+1} &= cN_t(1 - e^{-aP_t}) \end{cases} \quad (2.12)$$

where b is the intrinsic rate of increase in the prey population, K denotes the prey saturation value (carrying capacity), a the predator attack rate, and c the conversion efficiency of prey into adult predators of the next generation. The term $e^{b(1-\frac{N_t}{K})}$ denotes the prey-limiting factor where prey would reach a certain saturation value in the absence of predators and resembles the logistic growth curve.

Analysis of the local stability properties of the model was performed in the study by Beddington *et al.* [1]. The model exhibits various types of behaviour varying from an initial stable point, succeeded by stable limit cycles of increasing, non-integral period and increasing complexity, ultimately breaking down to cycles of integral period k , which then bifurcate to cycles of period

$2k$, $4k$, etc. These are followed by behaviour consisting either of limit cycles of high integral period or of aperiodic chaos. Figure 2.2 illustrates the models' sensitivity to changes in the prey growth rate parameter (b).

Figure 2.2: The population density cycles of the Beddington model exhibits increased high period cycles changing into chaotic behaviour with increases in the prey growth rate. Parameter values are set as $a=0.5$, $K=10$, $c=1$, $b=0.5$ and increased to $b=3$ in steps of 0.5 in figures starting from top left to bottom right.

The high period cycles or chaotic behaviour may be of considerable importance in interpreting the patterns of fluctuation shown by many prey populations in the field, as this implies the possibility of long term coexistence between predator and prey within well defined limits, but of a seemingly random nature. The temptation to ascribe such behaviour to environmental fluctuation is obvious. Thus a recognition that such behaviour may occur in an extremely simple, entirely deterministic predator-prey model is of considerable importance [1].

2.2 Deterministic vs Stochastic time events

The continuous time event models described thus far (Logistic growth, Lotka-Volterra and Ronsenzweig and MacArthur) assume that births and deaths happen continuously through time. Hence these models are deterministic time event models. Births and deaths, however, are stochastic events (chance occurrences) which happen in stochastic time steps². As mentioned earlier, for many species with seasonal life cycles, population growth is markedly discontinuous (in discrete steps). In nature, birth and natural death events of these species happen at specified times during the seasons. Although births and deaths are stochastic events, fixed discrete time steps (as in the Nicholson-Bailey model) are good approximations for these types of species, which is again a deterministic time event model but with fixed time steps rather than continuous time.

²Stochastic forms of continuous models are discussed in the book *Mathematical Ecology* by EC Pielou.

2.3 Mean-field assumption

At the heart of many population growth and interaction models lies an assumption that individual organisms encounter one another in proportion to their average abundance across space. This assumption is found in, for instance, the Lotka-Volterra equations for two interacting species i and j , expressed as the product of their mean densities $N_i N_j$. The mean-field assumption is most likely to hold as a good approximation when the physical environment of all organisms is homogeneous and 1) physical forces exist that cause strong mixing of organisms, 2) organisms themselves are highly mobile, and 3) organisms interact with others over long distances. As conditions depart from these, the mean-field assumption becomes less and less appropriate. A lack of mixing, whether due to the external environment or immobility of the organisms, generates neighbourhoods around individuals that deviate from the spatial averages. Differences in local environmental conditions become especially important if organisms only interact over short distances (integrating over large neighbourhoods can give spatial averages quite close to the mean field). The local environment organisms experience can then be quite different from the mean environment, averaged across the entire ecological habitat. Such departures from the mean field can feed through to the vital rates of individuals and can have fundamental effects on their dynamics [9].

2.4 Metapopulation Modelling and Simulation

In 1969 Richard Levins introduced a simple model to investigate the basic dynamic properties of metapopulations. He distinguished between the dynamics of single populations and a set of local populations, and he introduced a variable to describe the latter, $p(t)$, which in Levins's model denotes the fraction of habitat patches occupied by the species at time t . He encapsulated the relevant individual and population processes in two key parameters, e and m , which set the rates of local extinction and colonization of empty patches, respectively. He wrote an equation for the rate of change in p , and thereby specified the conditions under which p would be greater than zero. Levins's model is,

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = mp(1 - p) - ep \quad (2.13)$$

with the equilibrium value of p given by $p^* = 1 - \frac{e}{m}$. This simple model, analogous to the logistic model as a paradigm of local population growth, provided insight into metapopulation dynamics and was motivated by and applied to a pest control situation over a large region, within which local populations would fluctuate in asynchrony [12].

Levins's approach inspired a whole new way of thinking about spatially structured populations. The very simplified Levins model (which follows a mean-field assumption) is a valuable theoretical device, but understanding the dynamics of real metapopulations requires models with greater realism, and especially for management purposes, models that lead to more precise predictions [12]. Going beyond a model that considered only the scalar state variable p complicated matters greatly. With more desktop computing power, however, more realistic grid-based models emerged which previously would have been very difficult to analyse (without the help of computer based simulations)³. In these models the area of an ecological system is subdivided

³Simulation in broad refers to methods used to emulate or mimic real world systems or processes. It is often used to answer the 'what if' questions, studying the behaviour of a system over time and the effect of changing certain parameters in a model. A simulation process is usually associated with a computer and simulation software. This is evident in the correlation between the development of computers and the increase in use of simulations over the last few years.

into a grid of cells [9].

Two distinct types of grid-based models of predator-prey metapopulations have been studied. In ‘cell occupancy’ models the variables considered are how many cells are in each of a set of discrete states of prey and predator occupancy at a given time. These models all assume an inevitable within-cell progression from predator invasion to extinction. The second class of models, in contrast, describes within-cell dynamics explicitly, by standard single-population predator-prey models; migration among cells (subpopulations) is then added to these within-cell models [29]. Using grid-based models, the spatial dynamics of a metapopulation could now be explicitly simulated, and more precise predictions could be made [9].

2.5 Statistical stabilization from out-of-phase fluctuations

The simplest way in which space can promote persistence in predator-prey interactions is the mechanism proposed by Nicholson in 1933 [21], in which the populations in different regions of space are at different points in their unstable fluctuations. Not all areas are simultaneously at high or low densities. If the prey population is driven to low densities or driven extinct by the predator in some areas, it can be recolonized from other areas. This can only occur when the dynamics on different parts of the environment remain asynchronous. *Statistical stabilization* refers to the statistical result that if you sum up the population densities in a number of asynchronous, out-of-phase, subpopulations, the total density across the region has a much lower temporal variability than an individual patch. Through this mechanism the population density in each area continues to fluctuate, but the total population density across the region is relatively constant, and persistence of the system is enhanced. Spatial subdivision and limited migration ability of individuals is necessary for this mechanism to allow the dynamics in different spatial regions to remain asynchronous. In this study, however, PP and PE will be shown to contribute to asynchronous dynamics, even if migration rates are higher than the limited migration rates originally thought to allow asynchrony [5].

Chapter 3

Model formulation and justification

A predator-prey metapopulation is modelled by considering a habitat which is divided into discrete patches. This patchy environment is modelled as a two-dimensional arena in which predator and prey populations are distributed amongst a square grid of ‘cells’ or patches of an arena with width n . For the purposes of this study, only the class of models explicitly simulating within-cell dynamics have been considered. This allows the comparison of population densities in neighbouring cells, which is required to incorporate PE and PP in a model. As mentioned in the previous chapter, seasonal life cycles can be represented more realistically by the use of difference equations rather than differential equations. Within-cell dynamics are therefore simulated by assuming a discrete growth model. Among-cell dynamics (migration of individuals between neighbouring subpopulations/cells) are simulated by assuming inter-generation migration. This type of migration considers the growth process and migration to occur in two consecutive phases (*migration phase* and then the *reproduction and predation phase*) within the same time step¹ [7, 28].

3.1 Within-cell dynamics

Two discrete growth predator-prey models are considered during this study to determine the effect of PP and PE on spatial synchrony and hence metapopulation persistence. The first model considered assumes subpopulations in which co-existence of prey and predator is impossible in the absence of migration (subpopulations are described by the classic Nicholson-Bailey model). The second model considered assumes subpopulations where co-existence of prey and predator is possible without migration between patches (subpopulations are described by a prey-limiting extended Nicholson-Bailey model).

3.1.1 Classic model

In the *reproduction and predation phase*, we first consider one of the simplest discrete time models, namely the classical Nicholson Bailey model, in which predators simply search over a constant area and have unlimited capacity for consuming prey. This model has played a prominent role in the search for stabilizing mechanisms in predator-prey and host-parasitoid

¹In contrast with inter-generation migration, intra-generation migration considers the growth process and migration to occur simultaneously. According to [28], however, intra-generation migration is unrealistic for discrete generation populations.

interactions. As mentioned in chapter 2, it is always unstable and does not even allow persistence of the system (*i.e.* permanent coexistence of the interacting species) [16]. However, it has been shown that metapopulation persistence is possible through migration to nearest-neighbouring patches [7]. For the purposes of this study, the Nicholson-Bailey model is adjusted to incorporate spatial dynamics. The spatially adjusted Nicholson-Bailey model is given by

$$\begin{cases} N_{i,t+1} &= bN_{i,t}^M e^{-aP_{i,t}^M} \\ P_{i,t+1} &= cN_{i,t}^M (1 - e^{-aP_{i,t}^M}) \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

where $N_{i,t+1}$ and $P_{i,t+1}$ are the prey and predator population densities in patch i at time $t + 1$, $N_{i,t}^M$ and $P_{i,t}^M$ are the post-migration prey and predator densities in patch i at time t , b is the rate of increase in the prey population, a the predator attack rate, and c the conversion efficiency of prey into adult female predators of the next generation. Homogenous patches are assumed as well as random predation within each patch. Due to the uniform environment, all three parameters are spatially homogenous.

3.1.2 Improved model

As explained in chapter 2, the prey equation of the Nicholson-Bailey model requires modification to incorporate some saturation of the prey population or, in terms of predator encounters, a prey-limiting model. A more realistic model is proposed by Beddington *et al.* [1] which can be adjusted to incorporate spatial dynamics. The spatially adjusted Beddington model is given by

$$\begin{cases} N_{i,t+1} &= N_{i,t}^M e^{b(1 - \frac{N_{i,t}^M}{K}) - aP_{i,t}^M} \\ P_{i,t+1} &= cN_{i,t}^M (1 - e^{-aP_{i,t}^M}) \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

where $N_{i,t+1}$ and $P_{i,t+1}$ are the prey and predator population densities in patch i at time $t + 1$, $N_{i,t}^M$ and $P_{i,t}^M$ are the post-migration prey and predator densities in patch i at time t , b is the intrinsic rate of increase in the prey population, K denotes the prey saturation value, a the predator attack rate, and c the conversion efficiency of prey into adult female predators of the next generation. Again, homogenous patches are assumed as well as random predation within each patch. Due to the uniform environment, all four parameters are spatially homogeneous.

3.2 Among-cell dynamics

In the *migration phase* a certain fraction of adult predators and prey leave the patch from which they emerge and colonize the neighbouring patches, provided that predator and prey densities in neighbouring patches are more favourable, while the remainder stay behind to reproduce in their original patch. Many previous ecological models assumed ‘global’ migration where the underlying assumption is that all patches are equally connected to other patches (mean-field assumption). The migration and colonization of migrants in metapopulations, however, are certainly local processes in space, and hence the distribution cannot be described by the mean-field approximation [14]. It is therefore assumed that longer range migration can only occur through repetition of these single-patch movements over multiple generations. The resulting set of equations for the migration phase in each patch is given by

$$\begin{cases} N_{i,t}^M &= N_{i,t} + \frac{\mu}{1+\nu} \sum_j \left(\frac{N_{j,t} - N_{i,t}}{8} + \nu \frac{P_{j,t} - P_{i,t}}{8(P_{i,t} + P_{j,t})} (N_{i,t} + N_{j,t}) \right) \\ P_{i,t}^M &= P_{i,t} + \frac{\alpha}{1+\beta} \sum_j \left(\frac{P_{j,t} - P_{i,t}}{8} + \beta \frac{N_{i,t} - N_{j,t}}{8(N_{i,t} + N_{j,t})} (P_{i,t} + P_{j,t}) \right) \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

where $N_{i,t}$ and $P_{i,t}$ are the pre-migration prey and predator population densities in patch i at time t , $N_{i,t}^M$ and $P_{i,t}^M$ are the post-migration prey and predator densities, j runs over the nearest adjacent neighbours of patch i , μ and α denotes the maximum per capita migration rates of prey and predators respectively. The migration of prey caused by prey evasion is determined by the gradient of the predator density, and the migration of predators caused by predator pursuit is determined by the gradient of the prey density. Here, the parameters ν and β represent the effect intensities of PP and PE. This model was introduced by Li *et al.* [18] as an intra-generation migration model with the use of a within-patch Ronsenzweig-MacArthur growth model.

3.2.1 Boundary conditions

Certain assumptions has to be made for migration from patches on the boundary of the considered arena. Three types of boundary conditions have been suggested in previous studies, namely reflective, cyclic and absorptive boundary conditions. During this study, reflective boundary conditions are assumed where migrants are prevented from crossing the boundary, and remain in an edge patch. This effect applies seperately to the horizontal and vertical components of the attempted movement [7]. For example, a dispersing individual attempting to move south-east on the east boundary of the arena will actually move south. If it were at the south-east corner, it would remain in its starting patch. Reflecting boundaries ensure that the metapopulation is closed without individuals leaving [18].

Using cyclic² or absorptive³ boundary conditions is observed to have little effect, except that simulations with cyclic boundaries tend to produce symmetrical patterns (because of their more symmetrical mathematical properties) [7].

3.3 Problem Description

In this study we will investigate the effect of PP (β) and PE (ν) on spatial pattern formation and synchrony (and hence metapopulation persistence) by the use of simulations with different values of β and ν . Statistical stability, which will be measured by the standard deviation of temporal average population sizes, will be used as an indication of the extent in which subpopulations are synchronized. The fundamental requirement of persistence through migration is asynchrony of subpopulation fluctuations. Asynchronized subpopulations will have a much lower temporal variability. The average population size over time will also be used as an indication of metapopulation persistence. A higher average population size over time will indicate better persistence. From simulations, a parameter landscape will be deduced which will be used to investigate the effect of PP (β) and PE (ν) on statistical stability and average population sizes.

²Cyclic boundary conditions means that opposite edges of the arena are effectively joined together. This has the advantage that all patches are dynamically equivalent, with no edge effects (the arena size affects the dynamics of all patches equally). The nearest neighbours on the outside of edge patches are defined to be the patches on the opposing edges [7].

³Absorptive boundary conditions means that migrants moving across boundaries leaves the arena permanently, and in essence, these migrants are lost [7].

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter comprises two sections. The first section contains the simulation results in terms of spatial dynamics for the two models proposed in Chapter 3 while the second section contains the temporal dynamics and variation of the simulation with consideration of prey evasion and predator pursuit.

4.1 Simulation

For the purposes of this study, spatial dynamics have been explicitly simulated by the use of a MatLab script (see Appendix A). Simulations were started from a single cell in a 50x50 matrix with initial densities ($N_0 = 10, P_0 = 1$). Instantaneous maps from simulations of prey population density of both models are given. Different levels of shading represent different densities of prey population - blue squares represent low density, while red squares represent high density. The maps are single frames from simulations after 1000 generations, which take about 0.2s per generation on a 3.00GHz Pentium 4 with 1.00GB of RAM in a Windows XP environment. The predator population densities exhibit similar patterns to that of the prey population densities.

4.1.1 Classic model

As mentioned in Chapter 2, the subpopulations of the classic Nicholson-Bailey model are unstable to the point of extinction. It is known, however, that migration between subpopulations make metapopulation persistence possible. Without migration, the population within a single cell will go extinct (see Figure 2.1).

For different migration rates and no PP and PE, three general types of behaviour (spatial patterns) can be found, namely *spirals*, *spatial chaos* and *crystal lattices* as can be seen in Figure 4.1. With low migration rates ($\mu = \alpha = 0.1$) and no PP and PE, the model exhibits spatial chaos as illustrated in Figure 4.1 (a). As the migration rates are increased to $\mu = \alpha = 1$, complex pattern formations (spirals) start to form as illustrated in Figure 4.1 (c). With high predator migration rates and low prey migration rates ($\mu = 0.05, \alpha = 1$), the model exhibits crystal lattice patterns as illustrated in Figure 4.1 (b). The model without PP and PE have been investigated thoroughly by Comins *et al.* [7] and thus, for the purpose of this study, parameters a , b and c have been fixed at $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$ for all simulations.

Figure 4.1: *Instantaneous maps of prey population density for simulations of the migration model with Nicholson-Bailey local dynamics. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$, $\nu = \beta = 0$ and area width of 50 patches for all three, and a) $\mu = \alpha = 0.1$ (spatial chaos), b) $\mu = 0.05$, $\alpha = 1$ (crystal lattice), c) $\mu = \alpha = 1$ (spirals).*

Since the chaotic and crystal lattice spatial patterns already exhibit asynchrony, the effect of PP and PE on this model have been investigated only on spiral spatial patterns which exhibit synchrony to some extent. The parameters μ and α have therefore been fixed at either equal to 1 or 0.9. When the value of PP is equal to 1 and greater and $\mu = \alpha = 1$, no simulation starting from a single patch results in coexistence. This is due to the fact that the strong PP effect results in predators staying in the more favourable starting patch rather than migrating in the same wavefront as prey. With $\mu = \alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 1$, all prey migrate to the nearest neighbours from the starting patch, leaving predators behind with no prey to feed on as the wave moves away from the starting patch, resulting in predator extinction. For PP and PE values equal to and greater than 1, migration values have thus been set to 0.9.

Adding PE without PP to the model, does not seem to have any large effect on synchronous behaviour even for very high values of PE (see Figure 4.2 (a)–(c)). Spirals seem to break up a little into a greater amount of smaller spirals, but no asynchrony of neighbouring patches are found.

Figure 4.2: *Instantaneous maps of prey population density for simulations of the migration model with Nicholson-Bailey local dynamics and PE. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$, and area width of 50 patches, and a) $\mu = \alpha = 1$, $\nu = 0.9$, $\beta = 0$; b) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9$, $\nu = 3$, $\beta = 0$; c) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9$, $\nu = 100$, $\beta = 0$.*

Adding PP without PE to the model has more interesting results, with spirals being broken up into large complex chaotic structures for values greater than one (see Figure 4.3 (a)–(b)). For very large values complete asynchrony are found (see Figure 4.3 (c)). The type of asynchrony

found looks almost like a chess board — patterns are not necessarily chaotic with a variety of densities in different patches (which is one of the signs of asynchrony), but rather complete asynchrony of neighboring patches in the sense that every single patch has neighbours with very low and very high densities. This will always ensure that extinct patches are being recolonized from neighbouring high density patches.

Figure 4.3: *Instantaneous maps of prey population density for simulations of the migration model with Nicholson-Bailey local dynamics and PP. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$, area width of 50 patches, and a) $\mu = \alpha = 1, \nu = 0, \beta = 0.9$; b) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = 0, \beta = 3$; c) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 100$.*

Adding both PP and PE to the model does not seem to have any effect on the spatial patterns when the values of both parameters are less than one (*i.e.* when migration is more same species density dependent than PP or PE dependent). It still exhibits *spirals* (see Figure 4.4 (a)–(c)), however, for some parameter combinations the area between the spiral wavefronts seems to exhibit more variations in density than without PP and PE (Figure 4.4 (a)). This effect could improve statistical stability. As the values of PP and PE are increased from 0 to 1, spirals tend to form further apart and more distinguished. If spiral waves form too close to each other, they may annihilate each other, therefore increasing the probability of populations becoming extinct without being replaced [7]. The further apart spirals form from each other, the better, which is the case when adding PP and PE. In some cases, more spirals form when PP and PE is included in the model than when not (see Figure 4.4 (b)). Asynchronised behaviour are found for PE and PP values greater than one (see Figure 4.4 (d)–(f)). Again the asynchrony found in this model is rather interesting — not chaotic with a variety of densities in different patches, but asynchronised in the sense that every single patch neighbours high and low density patches. The patterns found with PP and PE incorporated in the model somewhat resembles the crystal lattice patterns found with no PP and PE (as seen in Figure 4.1 (b)), with the distinction that high density patches are connected in a maze-like way, instead of being isolated.

4.1.2 Improved model

As mentioned in Chapter 2, the subpopulations of the Beddington model exhibits various types of behaviour varying from an initial stable point, succeeded by stable limit cycles of increasing, non-integral period and increasing complexity, ultimately breaking down to cycles of integral period k , which then bifurcate to cycles of period $2k$, $4k$, etc. These are followed by behaviour consisting either of limit cycles of high integral period or of aperiodic chaos (see Figure 2.2). Investigation of synchronous behaviour between neighbouring cells would be difficult if within-cell dynamics exhibits chaotic behaviour. The parameters governing reproduction and predation in the improved model have therefore been fixed for all simulations, with $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$,

Figure 4.4: Instantaneous maps of prey population density for simulations of the migration model with Nicholson-Bailey local dynamics. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$, area width of 50 patches, and a) $\mu = \alpha = 1, \nu = 0.9, \beta = 0.9$; b) $\mu = \alpha = 1, \nu = 0.9, \beta = 0.3$; c) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 1$; d) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 3$; e) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 5$; f) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 10$.

$K = 10$, such that subpopulations exhibit high period limit cycles as seen in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: The population density cycles of the Beddington model with parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$, $K = 10$.

With low migration rates ($\mu = \alpha = 0.005$) and no PP and PE, the model exhibits spatial chaos as illustrated in Figure 4.6 (a). As the migration rates are increased to $\mu = \alpha = 1$, subpopulations are much more synchronized (see Figure 4.6 (a)-(f)). Investigation of the effect of PP and PE on synchrony was thus performed only on a relatively high migration rate (*i.e.* migration equal to 0.5) which exhibit synchrony.

Adding PE without PP to the model, does not seem to have any effect on synchronous behaviour even for very high values of PE (see Figure 4.7). Adding PP without PE to the model, also has little effect on synchronous behaviour even for very high values of PP (see Figure 4.8). Adding both PE and PP to the model, however, result in chaotic behaviour (with a variety of densities

Figure 4.6: Instantaneous maps of prey population density for simulations of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics without PP and PE. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $K = 10$, $c = 1$, $b = 0.5$, $\nu = \beta = 0$, and area width of 50 patches. a) $\mu = \alpha = 0.005$, b) $\mu = \alpha = 0.01$, c) $\mu = \alpha = 0.05$, d) $\mu = \alpha = 0.1$, e) $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$ and f) $\mu = \alpha = 1$.

in different patches) for PE and PP values large enough (see Figure 4.9). For $\nu = \beta = 10$ synchronous waves have completely broken down into chaos with asynchrony in population density cycles between neighboring patches.

Figure 4.7: Instantaneous maps of prey population density for simulations of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics and PE. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $K = 10$, $c = 1$, $b = 0.5$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = 0$, area width of 50 patches and a) $\nu = 0.4$, b) $\nu = 1$, c) $\nu = 100$.

4.2 Analysis

The simulated metapopulation discussed in the previous section were compared in terms of synchrony by using statistical stabilisation. The average density of a subpopulation has been

Figure 4.8: Instantaneous maps of prey population density for simulations of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics and PP. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $K = 10$, $c = 1$, $b = 0.5$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, $\nu = 0$, area width of 50 patches and a) $\beta = 0.4$, b) $\beta = 1$, c) $\beta = 100$.

Figure 4.9: Instantaneous maps of prey population density for simulations of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics and PP and PE. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $K = 10$, $c = 1$, $b = 0.5$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, area width of 50 patches and a) $\nu = \beta = 0.4$, b) $\nu = \beta = 0.6$, c) $\nu = \beta = 0.8$, d) $\nu = \beta = 1$, e) $\nu = \beta = 3$, f) $\nu = \beta = 10$.

calculated for each simulated generation and the variability of this average over 1000 generations were compared for different values of PP and PE. The variability of average densities over time for the classical model and the improved model are discussed in this section. Averages are given from the 400th generation to the 1000th generation to exclude effects at the start of simulations when the whole square grid is not occupied (especially for low migration rates).

4.2.1 Classic model

The metapopulation model without PP and PE does not show synchronous behaviour for certain parameter values when spatial chaos and crystal lattice patterns are observed. The parameter values exhibiting spirals are more synchronized and have thus been investigated further in this study. With no PP and PE, crystal lattice structures produces the smallest variability in temporal average densities (see Figure 4.10 (b)), while spiral structures produce the greater variability than chaotic structures (see Figure 4.10 (a) and (c)).

When only PE is taken into account, there seems to be a slight improvement in temporal variability for values below 1. However, for values of 1 and 2 it seems worse again, and for 3 the variability has decreased again except for two larger spikes in later generations (see Figure 4.11 (d)), for large PE values of 100 the variability seem to be greater than for the small PE

Figure 4.10: The average population size of the migration model with Nicholson Bailey local dynamics for both prey and predator populations when PE and PP are not taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$, and a) $\mu = \alpha = 0.1, \nu = \beta = 0$, b) $\mu = 0.05, \alpha = 1, \nu = \beta = 0$, c) $\mu = \alpha = 1, \nu = \beta = 0$.

values (see Figure 4.11 (e)). It's rather difficult to make any conclusion whether PE without PP results in an improvement of variability.

Figure 4.11: The average population size of the migration model with Nicholson Bailey local dynamics for both prey and predator populations with PE taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 1.2$, $c = 1$, $\beta = 0$, and a) $\mu = \alpha = 1, \nu = 0.9$, b) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = 1$, c) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = 2$, d) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = 3$, e) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = 100$.

When only PP is taken into account, there seems to be a slight improvement in temporal variability for values below 1 (see Figure 4.12 (a)). However, for values of 1 and 2 and 3 it seems worse again with large spikes in some generations (see Figure 4.12 (b)-(d)). For large PP values of 100 the variability improves for later generations up to the point of almost no variability (see Figure 4.11 (e)). Again, it's rather difficult to make any conclusion whether PP without PE results in an improvement of variability, however, in some cases where PP is large enough, there definitely is improvement in later generations.

Figure 4.12: *The average population size of the migration model with Nicholson Bailey local dynamics for both prey and predator populations with pp taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 1.2$, $c = 1$, $\nu = 0$ and a) $\mu = \alpha = 1, \beta = 0.9$, b) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \beta = 1$, c) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \beta = 3$, d) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \beta = 10$, e) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \beta = 100$.*

When both PE and PP are taken into account with values of less than one, it seems that some combinations of PE and PP effects tend to produce better statistical stabilization results than without PE and PP even for smaller PE and PP values (for example compare Figure 4.10 (c) with Figure 4.13 (a)). As PE and PP are increased to 3 and 5 a definite improvement in statistical stability can be seen. However, when PE and PP values are increased to 10, greater variability in temporal average densities can be seen (see Figure 4.13 (e)). With PE and PP values greater than 10, the model starts behaving quite odd, in the sense that the predator variability increases to such an extent that it overshadows the prey variability (see Figure 4.13 (f)), which results in less statistical stability.

The change in the standard deviation (variability) of temporal average densities for different values of PE and PP is illustrated in Figure 4.14 and Figure 4.15. Blue squares represent the lowest values of standard deviation, and red squares the highest values. For lower standard deviation values, more asynchrony in neighbouring patches would be expected. The results for PE and PP values smaller than 1 was excluded from these figures since the variability for some of these was too high to illustrate together with other values. The variability in the prey populations is definitely smaller for larger values of PE and PP. In the predator population however, it is difficult to conclude that higher PE and PP values result in better statistical stability. It does seem that higher PE values favour less variability in predator populations.

The change in the average population size over a 1000 generations for different values of PE and PP is illustrated in Figure 4.16. Blue squares represent the lowest average values, and red squares the highest values. The results show that an increase in either PE or PP result in higher averages, and thus better metapopulation persistence.

Figure 4.13: The average population size of the migration model with Nicholson Bailey local dynamics for both prey and predator populations with pe and pp taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 1.2$, $c = 1$, and a) $\mu = \alpha = 1, \nu = \beta = 0.3$, b) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 1$, c) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 3$, d) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 5$, e) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 10$, f) $\mu = \alpha = 0.9, \nu = \beta = 100$.

Figure 4.14: The standard deviations of temporal average size of the migration model with Nicholson-Bailey local dynamics for a) prey and b) predator populations when PP and PE are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.9$, ν and β are increased in steps of 0.5 from 1 to 5 .

4.2.2 Improved model

Synchronous behaviour for the metapopulation model have been investigated for high migration rates (*i.e.*, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$). With no PP and PE taken into account, the average densities increases in temporal variability with an increase in migration rate (see Figure 4.17 (a)–(f)), which indicates strong synchronous behaviour for high migration rates.

Figure 4.15: Top view of the standard deviations of temporal average size of the migration model with Nicholson-Bailey local dynamics for a) prey and b) predator populations when PP and PE are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.9$, ν and β are increased in steps of 0.5 from 1 to 5.

Figure 4.16: The average of population size of the migration model with Nicholson-Bailey local dynamics for a) prey and b) predator populations when PP and PE are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 1$, $b = 2$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.9$, ν and β are increased in steps of 0.5 from 1 to 5.

When only PE is taken into account, there seems to be no or only a slight improvement in temporal variability, even for large PE values (see Figure 4.18 (a)–(c)). This agrees with simulation results (see Figure 4.7 (a)–(c)) which show strong synchronous behaviour for high migration rates and high PE values.

When only PP is taken into account, the same progression holds, even large PP values results in no improvement (or very little improvement) (see Figure 4.19 and compare with Figure 4.8).

When both PE and PP are taken into account, synchronous behaviour becomes less. As PE and PP are increased, temporal variability starts to decrease up to the point where there is almost no temporal variability and complete chaotic spatial patterns (thus strong asynchronous behaviour) (see Figure 4.20 and Figure 4.9). From these results it can definitely be concluded that PE and PP together result in better statistical stability and thus improvement in metapopulation

Figure 4.17: The average population size of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics for both prey and predator populations when no PP and PE are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$, $\nu = \beta = 0$ and a) $\mu = \alpha = 0.005$, b) $\mu = \alpha = 0.01$, c) $\mu = \alpha = 0.05$, d) $\mu = \alpha = 0.1$, e) $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, and f) $\mu = \alpha = 1$.

Figure 4.18: The average population size of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics for both prey and predator populations when only PE are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = 0$ and a) $\nu = 0.4$, b) $\nu = 1$, c) $\nu = 100$.

persistence.

The change in the standard deviation (variability) of temporal average densities for different values of PE and PP is illustrated in Figure 4.21 and Figure 4.22. Blue squares represent the lowest values of standard deviation, and red squares the highest values. It seems that there exist a threshold value at which the synchronous wavefronts start to break down into more chaotic (and therefore asynchronous) behaviour. This threshold value seems to be more or less where both PP and PE are greater than 2.5 (see Figure 4.21). For lower standard deviation values, more asynchrony in neighbouring patches would be expected, and it is clear that for higher values of PP and PE neighbouring patches behave less synchronous. From Figure 4.21 it is also clear that if only PP or only PE ($\nu = 0$ or $\beta = 0$), temporal variability does not decrease (or

Figure 4.19: The average population size of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics for both prey and predator populations when only PP are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, $\nu = 0$ and a) $\beta = 0.4$, b) $\beta = 1$, c) $\beta = 100$.

Figure 4.20: The average population size of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics for both prey and predator populations when only PP are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, a) $\nu = \beta = 1$, b) $\nu = \beta = 3$, c) $\nu = \beta = 10$.

only slightly) with an increase in the value of PP or PE.

Figure 4.21: The standard deviations of temporal average size of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics for a) prey and b) predator populations when PP and PE are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, ν and β are increased in steps of 0.5 from 0 to 5.

Figure 4.22: Top view of the standard deviations of temporal average size of the migration model with Beddington local dynamics for a) prey and b) predator populations when PP and PE are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, ν and β are increased in steps of 0.5 from 0 to 5 .

The change in the average population size over a 1000 generations for different values of PE and PP is illustrated in Figure 4.23. Blue squares represent the lowest average values, and red squares the highest values. The results show that an increase in either PE or PP result in higher averages, and thus better metapopulation persistence. An interesting result is the fact that high predator density is obtained at high PE values together with either no PP , or high PP values, which indicates that predator persistence is enhanced by either pursuing to a large extent, are not pursuing at all at high PE values.

Figure 4.23: The average of population size of the migration model with Nicholson-Bailey local dynamics for a) prey and b) predator populations when PP and PE are taken into account. Parameter values set as $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.5$, $c = 1$, $\mu = \alpha = 0.5$, ν and β are increased in steps of 0.5 from 0 to 5 .

4.3 Conclusion

Results show that in both models PP and PE together can reduce spatial synchrony and result in the improvement of metapopulation persistence. When assuming Nicholson-Bailey within-cell dynamics, PE on its own has no effect on synchrony. PP, however, at very high intensities, does result in asynchrony. When assuming Beddington within-cell dynamics, PP and PE on their own has no effect on synchrony. In both models, PP and PE together can change spiral and circular waves to spatial chaos and therefore increase the spatial complexity and improve metapopulation persistence. Results also show that in both models either PP or PE can increase the average population size, thereby improving metapopulation persistence.

Chapter 5

Implications, limitations and future directions

5.1 Implications

The idea that space can promote persistence in predator-prey interactions was first proposed by Nicholson in 1933 [21], in which the populations in different regions of space are at different points in their unstable fluctuations. If the prey population is driven to low densities or driven extinct by the predator in some areas, it can be recolonized from other areas provided that the dynamics on different parts of the environment remain asynchronous. Spatial synchrony would therefore reduce the probability of metapopulation persistence. As mentioned in chapter 2, statistical stabilization refers to the result obtained when the total population density in asynchronous patches has a much lower fluctuation than that of an individual patch [5]. The average density of asynchronous patches would therefore also result in a much lower fluctuation.

One of the causes of synchrony is migration of individuals to nearby patches [7, 4]. In simple predator-prey metapopulation models with identical patches and homogenous local populations, even small migration rates can lead to synchrony because of phase locking [15]. Many mechanisms eliminating synchrony have been studied of which two of these, namely PP and PE, have been shown by Li *et al.* [18] to reduce spatial synchrony in overlapping generations. In this study, the effect of PP and PE in non-overlapping generations was investigated by first assuming subpopulations in which co-existence of prey and predator is impossible in the absence of migration (*i.e.* subpopulations are described by the classic Nicholson-Bailey model), and secondly assuming subpopulations where co-existence of prey and predator is possible without migration between patches (*i.e.* subpopulations are described by a prey-limiting extended Nicholson-Bailey model referred to as the Beddington model).

For large migration rates, systems are well-mixed, and differences between patches are mixed out. Results obtained from both models show that when PP and PE are both present in the model, these interspecific interactions lead to asynchronous behaviour in homogenous patches even without environmental heterogeneity. Therefore, they may be important factors in eliminating phase locking and reducing synchrony, and thus promote metapopulation persistence in predator-prey systems. However, with high migration rates, the effects of PP and PE must be stronger in relation to same-specie density dependent migration to result in asynchronous behaviour. Complete asynchrony in the Beddington model was found when only $\frac{1}{11}$ th of migration was due to same-specie density dependent migration, and $\frac{10}{11}$ th of migration was due

to PP and PE. For the Nicholson-Bailey model migration due to PP and PE was found to be somewhat lower, but still a bigger fraction due to PP and PE. With such dependence on high PP and PE effects to result in asynchrony for high migration rates, one has to start questioning the biological relevance of high PP and PE dependent migration (and no same-specie dependent migration). With lower migration rates, the onset of chaos starts with lower PP and PE effects, which might be more realistic in nature. The results in this study are consistent with the results of Li *et al.* [18] for the case where both PP and PE are present. When only one of PP or PE is present, however, the results are not consistent with that of Li *et al.* [18]. It has been shown that neither PP nor PE contribute to asynchrony in the Beddington model. It has also been shown that in the Nicholson-Bailey model, PP only contributes to asynchrony at very high values of PP, while PE only contribute slightly towards asynchrony at some values of PE. The results obtained in this study also show that local migration among homogenous patches results in complex spatial dynamics where spatial patterns are determined by the migration rates of prey and predator. When there are both PE and PP, self-organized spatial waves or spirals can be replaced by chaotic spatial distribution patterns or even static spatial patterns, which are consistent with the results of Li *et al.*

5.2 Limitations and Future directions

One of the big limitations in this study was the time constraint and also the computing power needed for some of the simulations. Therefore it was impossible to do a thorough investigation of both models in the set time period.

The Beddington metapopulation model exhibited a certain threshold value for PP and PE values (where synchronous waves starts to break down into asynchrony between neighbouring patches). This threshold value seems to be more or less where both PP and PE values are greater than 2.5, however, the specific threshold value can be determined by using smaller steps of increase in PP and PE (in this study the steps were chosen as 0.5 to shorten simulation time (see Figure 4.21)). It can also be determined by constructing a two-patch model and systematically analyze the influence of PP and PE on spatial synchrony by drawing bifurcation diagrams of the difference between the two patches versus ν and β for different migration rates. Sensitivity analysis is also required for the Beddington model for different values of a , b and c . In this study these parameters have been fixed to investigate synchronized behaviour more easily by constant fluctuations in subpopulations rather than chaotic behaviour in subpopulations.

The Nicholson-Bailey metapopulation model behaved unexpectedly for some parameter values, especially for predator populations. Large variations in temporal average densities were found for some combinations of PE and PP even though spatial patterns was asynchronised (see Figures 4.4 (e)–(f) and 4.13 (d)–(f)). More investigation is required in order to understand the effects of PE and PP on this model more thoroughly. A possible explanation might be due to the fact that subpopulations are unstable to the point of extinction, and fluctuate in increased amplitude before going extinct (see Figure 2.1). This instability and increased amplitude fluctuation might contribute towards the increase in standard deviations of temporal average densities. Also, looking at the spatial patterns for high PP and PE values, patches fluctuate in sync with a portion of patches exhibiting high density while the other portion exhibits low density with little inbetween density patches. Low density patches are recolonized by high density patches and these patches then reach high density levels after a number of generations. On the other hand, high density patches reach low density levels after only a small number of generations, which might result in the large variations of temporal average densities.

before the high density patches goes extinct (see Figure 2.1, the last fluctuation exhibit very high density and then extinction). Low density patches then start their fluctuation patterns and recolonize the extinct patches until they too reach their last high amplitude fluctuation before going extinct. This might result in large variations of temporal averages due to the increase in amplitude of fluctuations in high density patches.

In this study, predators have been assumed to immediately start with predation before maturing into adults, and therefore also assuming a constant functional response for all predators (young and mature). An interesting extension of this study might be to incorporate a maturation delay on predators and an increase in functional response with maturation. Maturation delay primarily determines cycle periodicity, while functional response controls the amplitude of fluctuations [30]. Furthermore, prey and predators have also been assumed to have the same life cycle time-steps. Another interesting extension to the model might be to assume different time-steps for prey and predator life cycles.

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Appendix A

Matlab Code

“There has never been an unexpectedly short debugging period in the history of computers.”

— Steven Levy

This appendix contains the Matlab code for implementations of the spatial simulations developed in Chapter 3. The .m files containing the code are divided into two categories, namely the Spatial Nicholson-Bailey code, and the Spatial Beddington code.

A.1 Spatial Nicholson-Bailey code

The file `Main.m` serves as a framework from where the different functions may be executed. Values of all parameters of the specific models are allocated here as well.

File: `Main.m`

```
%=====
%File executes the model of choice

clc;

n=50;
f=8;
a=1;
r=2;
s=1;
K=10;
m1=0.9;
m2=0.9;
endtime=1000;
time=1:1:endtime;
pe = 1:0.5:5;
```

```

function [ averageN, averageP ] = simulation_model_1(n,f,a,r,s,K,m1,m2,pe,pp,endtime)

delay = 0.02;

nameN = ['C:\MATLAB701\work\pics\SimN' int2str(pe*2+1) int2str(pp*2+1) '.gif'];
nameP = ['C:\MATLAB701\work\pics\SimP' int2str(pe*2+1) int2str(pp*2+1) '.gif'];

N=zeros(n);
P=zeros(n);

N(3,3)=10;
P(3,3)=1;

averageN=zeros(1,end);
averageP=zeros(1,end);

image(N);
I = getframe;
[X, Map] = rgb2ind(I.cdata,256,'nodither');
imwrite(X, Map,nameN,'gif','DelayTime',delay,'LoopCount',1,'WriteMode','overwrite');

image(P);
I = getframe;
[X, Map] = rgb2ind(I.cdata,256,'nodither');
imwrite(X, Map,nameP,'gif','DelayTime',delay,'LoopCount',1,'WriteMode','overwrite');

for t = 1:endtime
    [N,P] = migration(N,P,f,a,r,s,K,m1,m2,pe,pp);

    image(N*15);
    text(2,47,num2str(t),'FontSize',10,'FontWeight','bold','Color','w');
    I = getframe;
    [X, Map] = rgb2ind(I.cdata,256,'nodither');
    pause(delay);
    imwrite(X, Map,nameN,'gif','DelayTime',delay,'WriteMode','append');

    image(P*15);
    text(2,47,num2str(t),'FontSize',10,'FontWeight','bold','Color','w');
    I = getframe;
    [X, Map] = rgb2ind(I.cdata,256,'nodither');
    pause(delay);
    imwrite(X, Map,nameP,'gif','DelayTime',delay,'WriteMode','append');

    averageN(t) = sum(N(:))/numel(N);
    averageP(t) = sum(P(:))/numel(P);

end

%=====

```

Prey and population densities over time are calculated in the file `Migration.m`.

File: `Migration.m`

```

%=====
function [ newN, newP ] = migration(N,P,f,a,r,s,K,m1,m2,pe,pp)

n = size(N,1);

Nmigrate=zeros(n);
Pmigrate=zeros(n);

newN=zeros(n);
newP=zeros(n);

mN=zeros(n);
mP=zeros(n);

eN=zeros(n);
iP=zeros(n);

for i = 1:n
    for j = 1:n
        nbN = neighbour_reflective(N,i,j);
        nbP = neighbour_reflective(P,i,j);

        for t = 1:8
            mN(i,j) = mN(i,j) + (nbN(t) - N(i,j))/f;
            mP(i,j) = mP(i,j) + (nbP(t) - P(i,j))/f;

            if (P(i,j) + nbP(t) > 0)
                eN(i,j) = eN(i,j) + ((nbP(t) - P(i,j))*(N(i,j) + nbN(t)))
                    /(f*(P(i,j) + nbP(t)));
            end
            if (N(i,j) + nbN(t) > 0)
                iP(i,j) = iP(i,j) + ((N(i,j) - nbN(t))*(P(i,j) + nbP(t)))
                    /(f*(N(i,j) + nbN(t)));
            end
        end
    end

    if N(i,j) + (m1/(1+pe))*(mN(i,j) + pe*eN(i,j)) > 0
        Nmigrate(i,j) = N(i,j) + (m1/(1+pe))*(mN(i,j) + pe*eN(i,j));
    else
        Nmigrate(i,j) = 0;
    end
end

```

```

    if P(i,j) + (m2/(1+pp))*(mP(i,j) + pp*iP(i,j)) > 0
        Pmigrate(i,j) = P(i,j) + (m2/(1+pp))*(mP(i,j) + pp*iP(i,j));
    else
        Pmigrate(i,j) = 0;
    end

    newN(i,j) = r*Nmigrate(i,j)*exp(-a*Pmigrate(i,j));
    newP(i,j) = s*Nmigrate(i,j)*(1-exp(-a*Pmigrate(i,j)));
end
end

%=====

```

The neighbourhood of a cell is calculated in the file `Neighbour_reflective.m`.

File: `Neighbour_reflective.m`

```

%=====
function [neighbour] = neighbour_reflective(N,i,j)

n = size(N,1);

if (j==1)&&(i>1)&&(i<n)
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(2)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(3)=N(i-1,j);
    neighbour(4)=N(i-1,j+1);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j+1);
    neighbour(6)=N(i+1,j+1);
    neighbour(7)=N(i+1,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i,j);

elseif (i==1)&&(j>1)&&(j<n)
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j-1);
    neighbour(2)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(3)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(4)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j+1);
    neighbour(6)=N(i+1,j+1);
    neighbour(7)=N(i+1,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i+1,j-1);

elseif (j==n)&&(i>1)&&(i<n)
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j-1);
    neighbour(2)=N(i-1,j-1);
    neighbour(3)=N(i-1,j);

```

```
    neighbour(4)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(6)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(7)=N(i+1,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i+1,j-1);

elseif (i==n)&&(j>1)&&(j<n)
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j-1);
    neighbour(2)=N(i-1,j-1);
    neighbour(3)=N(i-1,j);
    neighbour(4)=N(i-1,j+1);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j+1);
    neighbour(6)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(7)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i,j);

elseif (i==1)&&(j==1)
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(2)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(3)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(4)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j+1);
    neighbour(6)=N(i+1,j+1);
    neighbour(7)=N(i+1,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i,j);

elseif (i==1)&&(j==n)
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j-1);
    neighbour(2)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(3)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(4)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(6)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(7)=N(i+1,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i+1,j-1);

elseif (i==n)&&(j==n)
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j-1);
    neighbour(2)=N(i-1,j-1);
    neighbour(3)=N(i-1,j);
    neighbour(4)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(6)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(7)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i,j);

elseif (i==n)&&(j==1)
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(2)=N(i,j);
```

```

    neighbour(3)=N(i-1,j);
    neighbour(4)=N(i-1,j+1);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j+1);
    neighbour(6)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(7)=N(i,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i,j);

else
    neighbour(1)=N(i,j-1);
    neighbour(2)=N(i-1,j-1);
    neighbour(3)=N(i-1,j);
    neighbour(4)=N(i-1,j+1);
    neighbour(5)=N(i,j+1);
    neighbour(6)=N(i+1,j+1);
    neighbour(7)=N(i+1,j);
    neighbour(8)=N(i+1,j-1);

end

```

A.2 Spatial Beddington code

The only file that differs from the spatial Nicholson-Bailey code is the `Migration.m` file. The reproduction and parasitism formula is adjusted for the Beddington model.

```

%=====
function [ newN, newP ] = migration(N,P,f,a,r,s,K,m1,m2,pe,pp)

n = size(N,1);

Nmigrate=zeros(n);
Pmigrate=zeros(n);

newN=zeros(n);
newP=zeros(n);

mN=zeros(n);
mP=zeros(n);

eN=zeros(n);
iP=zeros(n);

for i = 1:n
    for j = 1:n
        nbN = neighbour_reflective(N,i,j);
        nbP = neighbour_reflective(P,i,j);

```

```

for t = 1:8
    mN(i,j) = mN(i,j) + (nbN(t) - N(i,j))/f;
    mP(i,j) = mP(i,j) + (nbP(t) - P(i,j))/f;

    if (P(i,j) + nbP(t) > 0)
        eN(i,j) = eN(i,j) + ((nbP(t) - P(i,j))*(N(i,j) + nbN(t)))
                               / (f*(P(i,j) + nbP(t)));
    end
    if (N(i,j) + nbN(t) > 0)
        iP(i,j) = iP(i,j) + ((N(i,j) - nbN(t))*(P(i,j) + nbP(t)))
                               / (f*(N(i,j) + nbN(t)));
    end
end

if N(i,j) + (m1/(1+pe))*(mN(i,j) + pe*eN(i,j)) > 0
    Nmigrate(i,j) = N(i,j) + (m1/(1+pe))*(mN(i,j) + pe*eN(i,j));
else
    Nmigrate(i,j) = 0;
end

if P(i,j) + (m2/(1+pp))*(mP(i,j) + pp*iP(i,j)) > 0
    Pmigrate(i,j) = P(i,j) + (m2/(1+pp))*(mP(i,j) + pp*iP(i,j));
else
    Pmigrate(i,j) = 0;
end

newN(i,j) = Nmigrate(i,j)*exp(r*(1-Nmigrate(i,j)/K)-a*Pmigrate(i,j));
newP(i,j) = s*Nmigrate(i,j)*(1-exp(-a*Pmigrate(i,j)));
end
end

%=====

```
